

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

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MUNDARIJA

Ilm-fanga baxshida umr Baxtiyor Islamov	8
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishda “yashil” iqtisodiyotni keng tatbiq qilishning ahamiyati Gulnora Abdurahmonova Kalandarovna, Sanjar Baxodirovich G’oipnazarov	10
Brand Capital as a Determinant of Institutional Prestige and Student Choice in the Higher Education System ... Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna	16
Inson va atrof-muhit dialektikasi: nomutanosiblik ko’rsatkichlari va ekologik muammolar Butaboyev Maxammadjon Tuychiyevich, Maxmudov Nosir Maxmudovich	24
Yashil budjetlashtirish va uni O‘zbekistonda joriy etish istiqbollari Meylev Obid Raxmatullayevich, Gofurova Kamola Xayrulla qizi	30
Iqtisodiyotda ta’lim va fan integratsiyasining asosiy yo’nalishlari Yormatov Ilmidin Toshmatovich	35
Transport vositalari va yo’llar turizm transport infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning muhim omilidir Agzamov Shaxboz Akmalovich	39
Bank xizmatlarini raqamlashtirish orqali samaradorligini oshirish A. X. Salamov	44
Biznes-reja baliqchilik xo’jaligi rivojlanishi uchun asos sifatida Dosmuratova Shaxista Kengashovna	48
Mamlakatning investitsiyaviy jozibadorligi va uning lizing munosabatlari rivojlanishi bilan bog’liqligi Axmediyeva Aliya Toxtarovna	55
Turizmni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkabilovich	63
Tijorat banklari depozit operatsiyalari samaradorligini oshirish muammolari va ularni bartaraf etish yo’llari Shamsiyev Nodir Muratovich	67
Hududlarni rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning samaradorligini oshirish masalalari Shagazatov Oybek bahodirovich	72
Hududlar biznes muhitini rivojlantirish va samarali boshqarish yo’nalishlari Davlatov Sanjar Abdimannonovich	76
Ijtimoiy rivojlanish xulq-atvor paradigmasida yoshlarning tadbirkorlik faoliyatini tartibga solishning nazariy asoslari Mirzatov Baxtiyor Toxirovich	80
Korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatida raqamli transformatsiyaning muhim yo’nalishlari Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	84
O‘zbekistonda agroturizmni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish (Buxoro viloyati misolida) Yoriyeva Farangiz Murodillayevna	89
Innovatsion tadbirkorlik muhitini kompleks baholashda xalqaro tashkilotlar tajribasi Nazarova Umida Avazovna	94
Turizm faoliyatini davlat tomonidan tartibga solish samaradorligini oshirishning ayrim usullari Mirzaxodjayev Alisher Botirovich	98
Globalashuv sharoitida transchegaraviy suv resurslardan samarali foydalanishni boshqirish Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich	103
Surxondaro viloyati iqtisodiyotida kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikning o’rni va ahamiyati Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	108
Ta’lim muassasalarida xarajatlarni moliyaviy nazorat etishning samaradorligi tahlili Eshonqulov Davlatjon Rajabboyevich	113
Ta’minot zanjirini boshqarishda transport logistikasi usullarini takomillashtirish Zoxidova Nazokat Berdimurot qizi	119
Blokcheyn texnologiyasida xavfsizlik masalalari Mamadiyarov Zokir Toshtemirovich	123
Развитие цифровой трансформации банковского сектора Республики Узбекистан Абдурахманова Матлуба Махамдаминовна	129

Asosiy fondlarni hisoblash va baholash usullarini takomillashtirish istiqbollari.....	135
Rixsimbayev Odiljon Qobiljonovich	
Marketingda tovar harakati tizimini optimallashtirish va modellashtirish	141
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev, Kamola Abdujabborovna Pardayeva	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish uchun strategik taqsimlash strategiyalari: Investitsion Fond Portfellarning qiyosiy tahlili.....	148
Sultonboeva Munira bahodirovna	
Soliq munosabatlarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati: ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar.....	154
Axrorov Zarif Oripovich, Saidmurodov Feruz Sodiqjon o'g'li	
Взаимосвязь инвестиционной стратегии с оценкой эффективности инвестиционного проекта	159
С. С. Алиева, А. Назаров	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarning faoliyati va boshqaruv mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	167
Sheraliyeva Saida Azatovna	
Xizmat safari xarajatlari hisobining huquqiy asoslari	170
Ergashev Sarvar Xudoynazarovich	
Инклюзивное образование и его особенности.....	175
Зайнутдинова Умида Джалоловна	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulk va yer soliqlarini hisoblash va undirish samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	179
Qurbonov Muxiddin Abdullayevich	
Mamlakatda soliq qarzdorligi vujudga kelishining asosiy sabablari va ularni qisqartirish yo'llari.....	184
Hakimov Ulug'bek Furqat o'g'li	
Mulk qiymatini baholash tushunchasi, baholash obyektlari, baholanadigan qiymat turlari.....	188
Izbosarov Boburjon Bahriddinovich, Yoqubboyev Ilhomjon G'ulomjon o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda sug'urta xizmatlarining zamonaviy transformatsiyasi.....	193
G. Adilova	
Biznes subyektlarida samaradorlik masalalarini o'yinlar nazariyasi usuli bilan baholash.....	197
Mardiyev Nurali	
Yengil sanoatda "lean production" konsepsiyasini tatbiq etishning amaliy jihatlari.....	203
Yaxyayeva Inobat Karimovna	
Soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari va ularning tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatiga ta'siri tahlili	207
Borotov Sharofiddin Jumaqul o'g'li	
Ko'chmas mulk bozorini baholashning institutsional asoslari	213
Ishonqulov Nizamjon Fayzullayevich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida turizm xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	221
Amriyeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	
O'zbekistonning bank-moliya tizimi hamda unda Islom moliyasi instrumentlarini jalb etishdagi joriy tendensiyalar	226
Eshimov Alisher Dasmurodovich	
Tashqi savdoda notarif usullarni qo'llashning iqtisodiy oqibatlarini aniqlash metodologiyasi (rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi).....	234
Norqobilov Akobir Iso o'g'li	
Reklama xizmatlari va uning subyektlar samaradorligini oshirishdagi imkoniyatlari.....	240
Rabbimov Elbek Abdulloyevich	
Ijtimoiy siyosatni amalga oshirishda sog'liqni saqlash tizimini moliyalashtirish asoslari	245
Imonqulov Nuriddin Qo'shmon o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari biznes ekotizimini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	250
Shoymardonov Orziqul Jo'ra o'g'li	
Majburiy tibbiy sug'urtaning vujudga kelishi va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	256
Kenjayev Soxib Sayfiyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida zamonaviy soliq ma'murchiligini joriy etish orqali budjet-soliq siyosati samaradorligini yanada oshirish.....	260
Yuldasheva Shaxnoza Xojiakbar qizi	
Jahon iqtisodiyotining barqaror rivojlanishida derivativlar bozorining roli	266
Shokirov Mirkamol Mirolim o'g'li	
Boshqaruv hisobida mas'uliyat markazlarini tashkil etish masalalari.....	274
Sobirov Otabek Olimjonovich	

Davlat moliyasini boshqarishda moliyaviy nazorat usullaridan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	277
Kultayev Farxod Shavkatovich	
Tijorat banklari foydasi va rentabilik ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlilini takomillashtirish	281
Normo'minov Temurbek Sheraliyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida tijorat banklari aktivlar sifatini oshirish yo'llari	284
To'ychiyev Otabek Shamshiyevich	
Venchur kapitalining mohiyati va O'zbekistonda venchur tizimini rivojlantirishning institutsional asoslari.....	288
Tadjibayeva Nigora Gulomjonovna	
Innovatsiyalar: zamonaviy iqtisodiyot uchun innovatsion faoliyatni qo'llab-quvvatlash zarurati.....	293
Malikova Dilrabo Muminovna, Tursunov Jahongir Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Budjet daromadlarining shakllanishida egri soliqlarning ta'sirini ko'p omilli ekonometrik modellashtirishda tahlil qilish.....	297
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norqo'chqor qizi	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish yo'llari	302
Abdullayev Boburjon Akbaraliyevich	
Barcha tadbirkorlik subyektlariga teng raqobat sharoitini yaratishda soliq imtiyozlarining o'rni	306
Akbarov Akmalxon Akrom o'g'li	
Hisob siyosati va unda biologik aktivlar hisobini yoritib berish tartibini takomillashtirish	310
Mirzayeva Nargiza Batirovna	
Talabalarning oilali bo'lishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarga iqtisodiy baholashda yangicha yondashuv.....	314
O. U. Shomurodov, A. A. Suyarov, Z. U. Uroqov, J. S. Urazov, A. T. Ablahatov	
Ways to Use the Experience of Foreign Countries in Creating a Beneficial Business Environment for Entrepreneurship And Improving Taxation	319
Mukhlisa Ikramova	
Aholi turmush darajasini oshirishda moliyaviy savodxonlikning o'rni va iqtisodiy rivojlanishga ta'siri	325
Yusupov Muhammadali Soxib o'g'li, J.D. Xojiyev	
Temir yo'l sanoat korxonalarida ijtimoiy-mehnat munosabatlarini boshqarish bo'yicha xorijiy tajriba.....	329
Kadirova Sharofat Amonovna	
Механизм внедрения аутсорсинговой деятельности в АО “Ўзтемирўйўйловчи”	332
Н. Э. Кахарова	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni yanada rivojlantirish investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi	337
Sharipov Bobur Anvar o'g'li	
“STEKLOPLASTIK” MJCHning bozordagi strategik holatini tahlil qilish	342
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna	
Agrar sektorda ekologik toza mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarishning nazariy masalalari	348
M. Sh. Nazarova, Z. S. Kazakova	
Methodological Foundations of Bank Lending and Classification of Factors Affecting the Features of Obtaining Loans.....	353
Raxmanova Laylo bahodirovna, A. Karimova	
Agrosanoat klasterlarda tovar-moddiy zaxiralarni samaradorligini KPI orqali baholash uslubiyati	357
Toshpo'latov Azizbek Shermuxamadovich	
Faol tadbirkorlar faoliyatida kambag'al oilalarni iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy holatini yaxshilash imkoniyatlari.....	362
Salamov Ibrohim, Nazarova Maryam Sharifovna, Kazakova Zulayxo Saloxiddinovna, Jonibekov Faxriddin Beknazarovich, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna, Xamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Xudayberdiyeva Ma'rifat Umarovna	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar strategiyasi tahlilining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	369
Tursunova Shaxnoza Farxod qizi	
Процессы цифровизации АО “Hududgazta'minot”	373
Хусанов Кахрамон Нишонович	
O'zbekistonda aholi turmush darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	378
Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna, Eldorbekov G'ofurbek Iskandarbek o'g'li	
Aholi farovonligini oshirishda tadbirkorlik subyektlari uchun kredit tizimini takomillashtirish mexanizmi.....	381
Bobayev Isroiljon Abdinabiyevich	
Mamlakatga jalb qilingan xorijiy kapitalning tovarlar va xizmatlar importi salohiyatiga ta'sirini ekonometrik modellar bilan baholash.....	386
Saydullayev Azamat Jo'raqul o'g'li	

O'zbekistonda bank xizmatlari raqobatbardoshligini baholash mazmuni va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	394
Sh. Madraimov	
Kapital bozorida sug'urta kompaniyalar institutsional investor sifatida	397
Xasanova Lola Mamasharifovna	
Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasida institutsional islohotlarni yanada chuqurlashtirish va ko'p funksiyali raqamlashtirishning ilmiy asoslari	400
B. B. Berkinov	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi tijorat banklari orqali jinoiy yo'l bilan olingan daromadlarni legallashtirish mexanizmlari.....	409
G'afurov Umidjon Bahodir o'g'li	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda keksa fuqarolarning bandligini oshirish kam ta'minlangan aholi qatlamini qo'llab-quvvatlash usuli sifatida (Yaponiya tajribasi misolida).....	413
Karimov Bekzodjon Iloxovich	
Tashqi savdoni oshirishda boj-tarif siyosatini takomillashtirish mexanizmlari	420
Pardayev Ilhomjon G'ulomjon o'g'li	
Финансы или корпоративные финансы	426
Уринов Бобур Насиллоевич	
In Ensuring Economic Development in the Country Green Economy and its Features	432
Akhunova Shakhistakhon Nomonjanovna, Abdusattorova Mokhirabonu Abdugoppor kizi	
Tijorat banklarining investitsiya faoliyatini rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	437
Jo'rayev O'ktam Panji o'g'li	
Сокращение уровня бедности в Узбекистане.....	443
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
Paxtachilik sohasida ishlab chiqarish jarayonlari samaradorligini oshirishning innovatsion yechimlari va uning foydaga ta'sirini baholash	448
S. B. Inoyatov	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlar bilan ishlash amaliyotidagi muammolar va ularni barataraf etish yo'llari	453
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o'g'li	
Mahalliy budjet daromadlarining nazariy va ilmiy asoslari	460
O'lokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirish – aholi turmush farovonligini ta'minlashning muhim omili	463
Usmanov Baxodir Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli marketingni rivojlantirish zaruriyati	469
Xalmuxamedova Zebaxon Babaxanovna	
Tijorat banklari o'rtasidagi raqobatni rivojlantirish orqali fond bozorida aksiyalar narxini barqarorligini ta'minlash istiqbollari	473
M. Yuldosheva	
Konchilik sanoati korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirish mexanizmlarining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	480
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
O'zbekistonda banklar moliyaviy xizmatlari va ular sifatining amaldagi holati tahlili	487
Mirzayev Mirza Abdullayevich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining iqtisodiy samaradorlikning raqobatbardoshligini institutsional tahlil qilish mexanizmi.....	492
Saydullayeva Saodat Abdumajidovna	
Integratsiya sharoitida to'qimachilik sanoatining rivojlanishi	499
Ziyayeva Muhtasar Mansurdjanovna	
Auditorlik tekshiruvini tashkil etish va o'tkazish jarayonlarini takomillashtirish	503
Karamatova Noiba Husnitdinovna	
Davlatning iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning nazariy jihatlari	510
Mamatov Mamajan Axmadjonovich	
Экономическое сознание и экономическое мышление: теоретический анализ.....	517
Пардаев Мамаюнус Каршибаевич, Мухаммедов Мурод Мухаммедович	
O'zbekiston respublikasi tijorat banklari tomonidan qurilish korxonalarini kreditlashni takomillashtirish yo'llari	522
Sultanov Baxram Begdullayevich	

Роль искусственного интеллекта в современных технологиях медиаобразования в высших учебных заведениях.....	526
Самигова Гуландом Абдужаббаровна	
Talabalarga moliyaviy yordam dasturlari va ularning ta'lim sifatiga ta'siri	534
Mirzayeva Muhlisa Ubaydullo qizi	
Mintaqaviy investitsion jozibadorlik va investitsion siyosat: nazariy talqin	539
Muminov Akmal Tulkunovich	
Mamlakatni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotida oliy ta'lim tizimining ta'siri	543
Nasimov Adiz Azamat o'g'li, Baxtiyorova Jasmira Jasurovna, Axrorov Zarif Oripovich	
Respublikada fermer xo'jaliklarga xizmat ko'rsatishni rivojlantirish va agroxizmatlar bozorini davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash imkoniyatlari	548
Shukurov Ilhom Safarboyevich	
Turli mamlakatlarda oliy ta'limni moliyalashtirish yo'llari	555
Umarova Moxigul Maxmayunus qizi	
Dehqonchilikni innovatsion asosda rivojlantirishning xorijiy tajribasi.....	560
Yuldashev G'iyos Turabekovich	
Tijorat bank xizmat turlarini islomiy bank xizmatlari orqali rivojlantirish istiqbollari	564
Bayjanova Gozsal Sarsengaliyevna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotini baholash va hisobga olishning uslubiy jihatlarini takomillashtirish	570
Boltayev Abror Sayitmuradovich	
Секреты интересного урока в начальной школе.....	577
Гараева Олеся Владимировна	
Iqtisodiyotni barqaror rivojlanishda yashil iqtisodiyotning o'rni.....	580
Ibragimova Gulchehra Toxirovna	
Mahsulot va xizmatlarni raqamli transformatsiyasini amalga oshirish algoritmi.....	584
Kucharov Abrorjon Sobirjanovich, Bobojonov Azizjon Babaxanovich, Abdurakhmonov Abdumalik Abdurashidovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining soliq tizimi mamlakatda yashirin iqtisodiyot ulushini qisqartirish vositasi sifatida.....	591
Nabiyev Feruz Nurmurodovich	

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF BANK LENDING AND CLASSIFICATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE FEATURES OF OBTAINING LOANS

Raxmanova Laylo bahodirovna

Master of degree, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

A. Karimova

Scientific supervisor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Abstract: The article discusses the methodological foundations of bank lending, the essence of bank lending, as well as the systematization of approaches to classifying factors in the process of crediting enterprises, classified as business entities. The factors influencing the lending process are classified.

Key words: bank lending, consumer, tourism products, economy, tourism, private business, tourism activity, small enterprises.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bank kreditlash operatsiyalarining metodologik asoslari, bank kreditlashning mohiyati, shuningdek, tadbirkorlik subyektlariga kiruvchi korxonalarini kreditlash jarayoni omillarini tasniflash bo'yicha yondashuvlarni tizimlashtirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Bunda kreditlash jarayoniga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tasniflanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: bank krediti, iste'mol, turizm mahsulotlari, iqtisodiyot, turizm, xususiy biznes, turizm faoliyati, kichik biznes.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются методологические основы банковского кредитования, сущность банковского кредитования, а также систематизация подходов к классификации факторов в процессе кредитования предприятий, отнесенных к субъектам хозяйствования. Классифицированы факторы, влияющие на процесс кредитования.

Ключевые слова: банковское кредитование, потребитель, туристические продукты, экономика, туризм, частный бизнес, туристическая деятельность, малые предприятия.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the field of tourism services is one of the rapidly developing areas of the economy of many developed and developing countries of the world. In this regard, in the world practice, a significant number of scientific studies have been conducted regarding the study of credit support for enterprises in the field of tourism services. The methodological basis is studied and the mechanism of crediting enterprises is analyzed, as well as scientific developments are made in the field of improving credit support for enterprises. As a result of these studies, noteworthy scientific and theoretical concepts and experience of lending to enterprises in the international practice of lending are collected. However, the tourism enterprises we study today are at different levels of development, and the results achieved at the international level of improving the mechanism of their credit support are not sufficiently disclosed. The application of world experience and knowledge in individual countries requires more in-depth scientific research.

ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE USED

Various aspects of lending to enterprises are reflected in the works of many domestic and foreign scientists-economists, who analyze certain scientific, theoretical and practical aspects of lending to subjects of the tourism services sector. Foreign researchers of which include: S. I. Ozhegova, Ya.N.Kalugina, V.T. Batyckho, N.E. Sokolinskaya, L.M. Kupriyanova and others. Also, many domestic scientists worked on issues in the field of lending to enterprises, including: E.Abdullayev, Sh.A.Yuldashev, J.Zainalov, Sh.Abdullayeva, N.Urmanova, T.Malikov, A.Baymuratova, I.Rakhmanova, D.Tadjibayeva, Zh. Isakova, L.Zoyirova and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted using the methods of scientific abstraction, induction, and synthesis.

The main part. For many years, scientific researchers have proposed a variety of definitions that characterize various aspects of the lending process, based on the essential characteristics of lending, in relation to its structural, temporal, object and subject components.

In order to understand the methodology of lending to enterprises, first we will consider the very concept and essence of lending. A loan in Latin means “loan”, in other words, it is an economic relationship in which one party receives from the other party money, goods/things that are not prohibited by the relevant legislation for transfer, and promises to provide compensation (payment) or return resources in the future. In fact, a loan is a legal formalization of an economic obligation ^[1].

S.I.Ozhegova asserts that credit is, firstly, a loan, the provision of valuables (money, goods, etc.) in debt; secondly, commercial trust ^[2]. Credit accumulates the released capital, serves its receipt and ensures the reproduction process. Accelerates the process of money circulation, participates in the regulation of market relations. Ya.N.Kalugina believes that the main type of credit is a bank loan, which is understood as: a form of transfer of value based on repayment, urgency and payment; a form of accumulation and placement of temporarily available funds of business entities in order to stimulate the turnover of fixed and current assets and advance the reproduction process; a factor of production ^[3].

In general, the lending process is understood as the movement of bank loans or loans in the form of a sequence of organizational stages, expressed in the form of changes in lending periods and mechanisms. Lending itself as an economic phenomenon in modern science and practice is divided into banking and non-banking, in connection with which the study will consider both the process of bank and non-bank lending. Next, we will consider the essence of bank lending (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The essence of bank and non-bank lending (developed by the author on the basis of ^[5])

The conducted research shows that the process of lending to business entities depends on a large number of factors that affect both positively and negatively the performance of many commercial banks. The classification of internal and external factors that affect the process of crediting business entities is carried out and justified by scientists-economists, in particular, M.Y.Kostyko. L.M.Kupriyanova in her monograph ^[6] identifies a classification of factors that affect the development of the process of crediting business entities.

According to the Russian scientist V.T. Batycho bank lending refers to economic (monetary) relations, in the process of which temporarily free funds of the state, legal entities and individuals accumulated by credit organizations are provided to economic entities (as well as citizens) on the terms of repayment ^[4].

Next, we will consider the classification of factors in the process of crediting business entities (see: Table 1).

Table 1: Approaches to classifying factors in the lending process subjects of entrepreneurial activity

The author	Features of the classification of factors in the process of crediting business entities	Disadvantages of the approach to classification
James K.	Identification of three main groups of external factors of lending субъектов сферы to business entities (legal, tax and financial environment)*	Limited view of the credit process
A. A. Thompson	Identification of various external factors, namely: macroeconomic, legislative, regulatory acts, social values and lifestyle, demographic, technological **	Attention is paid to macroeconomic factors that are related to economic characteristics, industry affiliation of the company.
M. Y. Kostykova	Identification of external factors that affect the bank's loan portfolio for the following purposes: medium and small enterprises, such as: strategy and policy of the bank; crisis and falling living standards of the population; demand for loans ***	Factors of influence can be supplemented. Thus, the features of lending (which are determined by the processes that take place in banks when making decisions on issuing loans) are closely related to the features of obtaining loans, which are specifically Russian-specific and are not inherent in the banking systems of developed countries

* Ван Хорн, Дж.К. Основы финансового менеджмента / Дж.К. Ван Хорн. –М: Вильямс, 2001. – 988 с.

** Томпсон, А.А. Стратегический менеджмент: концепции и ситуации для анализа / А.А. Томпсон, А.Дж. 12-е издание. – М.: Вильямс, 2013. – 924 с.

*** Костыкова, М.Ю. Банковское кредитование МБ и направления его совершенствования в Российской Федерации: диссер. на соис. уч.степ. к.э.н. Воронежский гос.универ. – Воронеж, 2015. -С.47. с. 173-189.

Classification of factors in the process of crediting enterprises classified as business entities is appropriate in the context of driving forces, the impact of which can be considered below. (see: Figure 2)

Figure 2: Classification of factors influencing the process crediting of business entities (developed by the author on the basis of [6])

Since the presented classification is a kind of division of influences exerted on the lending process of enterprises classified as business entities, it should have all the rules used in the operation of complex and informative division of the volume of synthesizing changes in this area. The research should be focused on complementing and systematizing the group of factors identified by us that influence the process of lending to business entities.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, summarizing the above, it is necessary to identify a significant set of factors that affect the process of lending to business entities. Identification of factors influencing the development of the lending process of subjects proves that the main processes related to lending require further improvement. In addition, the final classification of factors, taking into account the additions made, allows us to clearly identify the basis for the effective development of the lending process for business entities.

Thus, in order to minimize the factors affecting the lending process, it is necessary to strengthen the theoretical and practical training of the bank's staff, introduce the use of specialized assessment of the financial situation of borrowers, and develop a competitive line of credit offers of commercial banks.

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